

PREPARATION AND PARTICIPATION IN SPORTS COMPETITIONS, TYPES OF COMPETITIONS

Abduraxmonov Xayrullo Xakimjanovich

Faculty of physical culture

teacher of the department of theory of physical education

Jabaraliyev Bekzodjon To'lqinjon o'gli

student of the faculty of physical culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11505458>

Annotation

This article shows about the effectiveness of conducting extracurricular activities in volleyball

Key words

Sports, physical education, competition , practitioners, techniques, movement, physical quality, skill, purpose.

In volleyball, two effective methods of physical education are added: play and competition. First of all, volleyball is part of sports games and becomes rich with game exercises. Secondly, those who are engaged in the form of a game are well mastered the program of the game. Thirdly, the competition situation will be present in the volleyball game itself, and conducting most exercises in a competitive manner will ensure the maximum attraction of student strength . All this suggests that competitions play a big role in halting physical education tasks.

Sports competitions are inextricably included in the system of training volleyball players. They are not only the direct purpose of training, but also a means of special training. Now it is difficult to achieve success in sports. Constant participation in competitions, on the other hand, increases the acquisition and knowledge of the necessary competitive qualities, place qualifications and tactical skills. Competitions tend to have slow content and include special qualities that are only nurtured in competitions.

It is necessary to try to make sure that the competitions must be held within the specified periods. January – March is the best time for district and City competitions, and November – December is the best time for intra-school competitions. The fact that the number of competitions is very small interferes with normal orientation of the sectional training training process. For 15-17 youth, respectively, the number of games in mini - volleyball for children of younger age 30 (14-16 are calendar competitions) will be 10-14 (6-8 are

calendar), in addition, it is better for them to hold competitions in the technique of the volleyball game(2.2. - table).

Those involved are required to follow the same game tactic.

Table 3.2

Competition load size (number of games per year)

Study groups (Age, year)	Number of games in a year	
	total	From them according to the calendar
Those in training	24	12
12-14-1 year deals	34	16
13-15-2 years involved	44	20
14-16-3 years involved	50	26
15-17-4 years involved		
Sports improvement groups	60	32
16-18-1 year deals	65	36
17-19-2 years involved	70	40
18-20-3 years involved		

Volleyball is a team sport, and the result of participating in competitions is visible in the end, strengthening the team members in a team way. To be a good effective game in a team way, volleyball players must be individually prepared to compete. It is impossible to ensure that all young volleyball players participate in official competitions, but it is necessary to prepare them all in the same way. To ensure that the participants participate in competitions one hundred percent, it is necessary to conduct volleyball matches and competitions in the college itself. These competitions should have an official character with the best training gurus in appearance and age, awarding the best teams and winners. In competitions on technical and physical training, a young volleyball player fights for himself, and here the qualities of the most difficult fighting are brought up. In volleyball preparatory and competitive games, these qualities are transferred to team events.

The members of the volleyball section and the bolláng preparatory group participate in competitions based on the “Alpomish” and “Barchinoy” test standards program on an equal footing with all this, and this serves as a test for general physical fitness. Such competitions are held in a multicooker style (running, jumping, throwing) and together (running, jumping, throwing).

For example:

- 1) jump above the place of standing, jump far from the place of standing, jump three letters from the place of standing;
- 2) when sitting, jumping, throwing the filling ball with the grip behind the head;
- 3) run to 30 m, run to 92 m with a change of direction, run to 3x10 m, run to 6x5 M; 4) run to 30 m, jump.

Competitions at the beginning of the academic year in physical serve as control tests and can be viewed as training training work. Competitions in technical training increase interest in mastering the technique of the game of volleyball in children, while the teacher allows young athletes to see the techniques of the game. The program of competitions includes the first and second passes of the ball, ball passes to a specific mark through the ball, offensive shots to a specific target. For children 8-12 years old, it is necessary to hold competitions in action games, special relay teams and Games (volleyball prep), mini-volleyball. Games are included that indicate the speed of response movements and mainly agility.

These more team games are "flying target", "hunters and ducks", "day and night", "fight for the ball". Of course, it is also necessary to pass basketball and handball competitions. Various methods of moving to the relay teams (with side steps, with a jump on one leg, etc.), passing filler balls, drum augments, changes in the direction of movements.

During the conduct of the internal competitions of the college, it is necessary to carry out complex tests in accordance with the purpose: to take into account the results in volleyball or mini-volleyball, to take into account the results in physical fitness as well (Table 2.3).

In volleyball, it is advisable to hold the competition by the same age (15 years, 16, 17 years), since in this it is achieved to participate all students in the competition in the same way. Competitions are held in full line-up (6x6) and in incomplete line-up 5x5, 4x4, 2x2, 1x1. Such competitions improve the qualities of competing when combined with competitions in physical and technical training, which are then prominent during full-squad teamwork in volleyball. Mini-volleyball competitions are held for students aged 10-12. The rules of Mini-volleyball differ slightly from each other from the rules of volleyball.

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In order to more effectively prepare young volleyball players, it will be advisable to include specific situations in the rules of competitions: play the ball into the game input (herd) only from below directly, when receiving the herd, transfer the ball to zone a) 3; B) Zone 4; transfer for the shot only in the position facing the attacker (a); B) to him in the position standing with his back.

Table 3.3

The procedure for replenishing groups and training in sports sections

Naming groups	Year of fogging	Pupils Age (year)	Number of students in the group	Number of study hours per week	Number of study hours in a year
Initial preparation	1	10-12	15	8	416
	2	11-13	15	8	416
Training training	1	12-14	12	10	520
	2	13-15	12	12	624
	3	14-16	10	15	780
	4	15-17	8	18	936
Sport Taco-milization	1	16-18	6	24	1248
	2	17-19	6	24	1248
	3	18-20	6	30	1560

Competition rounds

The following volleyball competition rounds will be aimed at the school:

1. Visual performances of high-level teams;
2. Friendly meetings with other schools;
3. One-day competitions-blitz tournaments;
4. Cup or trophy competitions;
5. School Premiership.

Exhibition meetings are organized in order to popularize volleyball and demonstrate sports skills at the school. For this, teams that have achieved a high level of sports training in the previous period in improving the work of the

section are invited. When a competition is held in the school hall between highly skilled teams, this task is solved in an excellent way.

Friendly matches will be essential to prepare the school team for district or city competitions. If friendly matches are traditionally played with strong opponents they serve as a tool in gaining interest in volleyball. Tournaments differ from other competitions in that over the course of a day, several teams will participate in this competition. Therefore, it is good to spend weekends in these tournaments. Holding competitions for cups or prizes should become a tradition at school. They are dedicated to the memory of distinguished dates or alumni who attended and served at the school. These competitions are held by the cutting method.

The school Premiership is the only competition in the academic year to determine the school's strength team and the remaining seeded teams. The high performance of the school championship competitions in a circular fashion

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